

THEORETICAL BASIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

Juraeva Khurshida Pirmat qizi

Tashkent city Yashnobod region "BABM" English teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10638006>

Annotation: in this article, the theoretical views of scientists of different nationalities about phraseological units are studied and discussed.

Key words: phraseology, phraseological layer, phrase, phraseological unit, phraseological compound, phraseological integrity.

Language is the mirror of every nation, its true reflection. As long as there is a language, the nation is alive. It is not for nothing that language is compared to a mother, a person cannot live without seeing his mother, without feeling her pure love and affection. In our country, attention is paid to the issue of language, especially to foreign languages. In this place, the ideas and views of our great-grandfathers, the devotees of enlightenment at the beginning of the last century, come to mind. For example, Mahmudhoja Behbudi emphasizes the importance of knowing the works of world sages, truly enjoying the masterpieces of world literature, understanding the times, and learning a foreign language for development¹.

Studying the language in terms of its lexical richness, applying modern methods of teaching them to the teaching process is very relevant today and supports its priority in accordance with the requirements of the time.

Ensuring unity and consistency in language teaching, improving textbooks and study guides, reflecting in them the news of science, especially in the field of linguistics, highlighting current and future tasks, applying scientific news through modern methods in the teaching process. the development of every language demands its necessity today. In linguistics, there are various possibilities for the enrichment of the vocabulary, and the vocabulary mainly consists of words. By lexical units, we mean not only individual words, but also fixed word combinations, phrases, fixed expressions, phraseology.

The main focus of phraseology as a branch of linguistics is to study the nature of phraseology and their classification signs, as well as to determine the laws of use of phraseology in speech. The most important problem of phraseology is to distinguish phraseologisms from word combinations formed in speech and to determine the signs of phraseologisms on this basis. Depending on the specific differences between idiomatic phraseology, phraseological combinations and stable sentences (proverbs and proverbs, other phraseology equivalent to a sentence), many researchers understand phraseology in two ways: narrow and broad. When it is understood in a broad sense, the circle of phraseology includes proverbs and sayings, stable sentences characteristic of folklore, and some forms of communication. However, this issue, that is, the issue of understanding phraseologies in a broad sense, is still controversial.

Although the term "phraseology" is derived from the Greek word "frama" (phrasis-expression, speech package), this term serves to express different meanings. For this reason, the term phraseology is used in linguistics in two senses: in the sense of the totality of existing phraseological units in the language, and in the sense of the field that studies such units. So, phraseology means the science of phrases.

¹ <https://www.gazeta.uz//Xorijiy> tillar: manzilga eltuvchi yo'l adog'i qayerda?

Phraseological units consist of two or more words, structurally equivalent to a compound or a sentence, alternative to a word, as stable lexical units that have a portable meaning and fulfill their lexical-semantic, functional and syntactic functions. They are distinguished from other units of the language. Phraseological units together with the lexicon make up the vocabulary of the language.

Although the origin of phraseological units is considered very ancient, their research is relatively young.

The term phraseology is the Greek word *phrasis* - phrase, *logos* - concept, doctrine, and is interpreted as a branch of linguistics that studies phraseological units. In linguistics, they are studied by such terms as phraseologism, phraseological unit, phrase, phrase, idiom.

The main tasks or issues of phraseology: to determine the consistency of phraseological content and in this regard to study the symbolic nature of phraseology; description of homonymy, synonymy, antonymy, polysemy, and variation of phraseology; to determine the specific features of the words used in phraseology and their specific meanings; to clarify the relationship between phraseology and word groups; determine their syntactic role; studies the formation of new meanings of words within phraseological units and develops the principles of separating other phraseological units, methods of their study, classification and description in dictionaries. On the basis of unique, diverse methods developed in phraseology, the phraseological composition of the language is classified according to different: structural-semantic, grammatical, task-methodical bases.

The principle of structural-semantic classification is the main one. Different features of phraseological expressions can be determined by classification based on external form. In this classification, more attention is paid to the number of words in phraseological expressions. As a result of the classification, it is possible to determine how many words are made up of phrases according to their nature. Many linguists are of the opinion that phraseological expressions are only more than two words. But observations show that phraseological expressions consist of two, three or more words. But some linguists think that one-word phrases are synonyms.

In this sense, the phraseological scientist A.V. Kunin justified the opinion that the author of most of the English phraseology is unknown, and they were created by the people. But it is possible to determine the sources of origin of some phraseological units². In this sense, phraseology is a microsystem that is part of the general system of language, and this system reflects past heritage, values, and is passed from generation to generation. Most of the phraseological units that make up the system are a rich source of a given language. The relationship between phraseological units and their main components makes up the phraseological system. Phraseologisms are combinations of words composed of more than one word, stable in meaning and form. Phraseologisms are used figuratively and figuratively and have historical standards and methods of use, and their meaning is clarified in the course of a specific speech. Phraseologisms are in the form of phrases or sentences, they differ from sentences that are speech units. As a lexical unit, they are close to words in many respects, many features characteristic of words are also characteristic of phraseologisms³.

² Кунин А.В. Курс фразеологии современного английского языка. – М.: 1995. – 109 с.

³ Алефиренко Н.Ф., Семененко Н.Н. Издательство «Флинта», 2009. – С. 346.

In particular, according to Professor SH. Rakhmatullaev, one-word expressions are formed at the highest stage of development of idiomatic expressions⁴. Expressions of this type are expressed by a compound word or a single word, they differ from compound words in that they cannot express a direct thought. An idiomatic meaning can also be understood through a single word. But it is difficult to call such words a phrase. Because a phrase must consist of a combination of words. The opinions of V. V. Vinogradov, A. Abakumov, and A. Shakhmatov are valuable. Idiomatic words consist of only one component and have an idiomatic meaning. But the expression cannot mean the characteristics it reflects. According to Academician V.V. Vinogradov, the development of phraseological units should start from phraseological unity and turn into phraseological compounds. Based on this opinion, Sh. Rakhmatullayev's opinion that "Idiomatic words are formed on the basis of phraseological combinations" is justified. Phraseological combinations mainly consist of a combination of words, in other words, phraseologisms are a separate unit of the language, which according to their structure are freely connected or equivalent to a sentence, fully or partially semantically reshaped figurative, stable word combinations. includes. Most of the phraseologisms were created by the people, both in English and in other languages, their authors are not known, the sources of origin are not clear.

References:

1. Алефиренко Н.Ф.,Семенов Н.Н. Издательство «Флинта», 2009.
2. Кунин А.В. Курс фразеологии современного английского языка.–М.: 1995.
3. Rahmatullayev Sh. O'zbek tili frazeologiyasining asosiy ma'no turlari. –Т.: Akadem nashr. 1985.
4. Телия В.Н. Что такое фразеология, М., “Наука” , 1966.
5. Umarov E.A Frazeologik lug'at, Xazoin-ul maoniy A.Navoiy, Toshkent 1971.

⁴ Rahmatullayev Sh. O'zbek tili frazeologiyasining asosiy ma'no turlari. – Т.: Akadem nashr, 1985. – 109 b.